

Economics and Business Quarterly Reviews

Ramos, A., Koesmono, T., Ellitan, L., & Otok, B. W. (2023). The Influence of Strategic Leadership, Organizational Learning, And Organizational Culture on Organizational Performance Through Organizational Citizenship Behavior in Timor-Leste National Police Using Structural Equation Modeling. *Economics and Business Quarterly Reviews*, 6(1), 187-196.

ISSN 2775-9237

DOI: 10.31014/aior.1992.06.01.497

The online version of this article can be found at:

<https://www.asianinstituteofresearch.org/>

Published by:
The Asian Institute of Research

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The Influence of Strategic Leadership, Organizational Learning, And Organizational Culture on Organizational Performance Through Organizational Citizenship Behavior in Timor-Leste National Police Using Structural Equation Modeling

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Abstract

The National Police of Timor Leste (PNTL) is in charge of the country's internal security. As a result, the PNTL, as an institution, should prepare dependable human resources to ensure the stability of the state by applicable regulations. The study's findings using the structural equation modeling (SEM) approach show that the organizational performance model fits the GoF criteria. Strategic Leadership, Organizational Learning, Organizational Culture, Organizational Citizenship Behavior, and Organizational Performance are all convergently and discriminantly valid and reliable indicators. The ability to manage change, build cooperation and a sense of belonging, and be visionary is the dominant indicators of strategic leadership. Systems thinking, mental models, learning teams, and personal mastery are the most important indicators of organizational learning. Bureaucratic culture, innovative culture, and supportive culture are the dominant indicators of Organizational Culture. Willingness to Tolerate without Complaint and Involvement in Organizational Functions are the dominant indicators of Organizational Citizenship Behavior. Service Quality, Responsibility, Accountability, and Productivity are the most important indicators of Organizational Performance. Organizational Citizenship Behavior, Strategic Leadership, Organizational Learning, and Organizational Culture all have an impact on organizational performance. Furthermore, Strategic Leadership, Organizational Learning, and Organizational Culture all have an impact on organizational citizenship behavior.

Keywords: Organizational Citizenship Behavior, Organizational Culture, Organizational Learning Organizational Performance, SEM, Strategic Leadership

1. Introduction

Polcia Nacional de Timor-Leste (PNTL) is the National Police of Timor Leste, which is responsible for the internal security of Timor Leste under the PNTL for Defense and Security (Ministério da Defesa e Segurança), especially the Secretariat of State for Security Affairs (Secretaria de Estado da Segurança). Now the PNTL is under the control of the PNTL Dalam Negeri (Ministério do Interior). The PNTL was established on March 27, 2000, when Timor-Leste was still under UN administration (UNTAET), with the Commissioner being the Superintendent (Superintendent) (BBC Indonesia, 2016). Human beings are the main concern in the Police Institution as an organization because humans play a significant role in an organization. So humans must be managed as employees and not as machines. Therefore, the organization must manage employees as the main and most important factor for its success. According to Wirman & Alwi (2014), the role of humans is very important in the achievement of organizational goals in both private and public organizations, so elements of the workforce or staff need to be given proper attention by management or leaders in each agency. Therefore, employees are given proper motivation to work well.

The concepts of universal policing, the duties and functions of the PNTL listed in the RDTL constitution and laws, and the philosophy adopted by the PNTL all point to the need to organize and develop police institutions that can answer the need for security and public order. Therefore, as an institution, the PNTL should prepare reliable human resources to ensure the stability of the country by applicable regulations (Fundasaun, 2014). Developing good human resources and using them appropriately can help government agencies become dynamic and achieve maximum work performance. Work motivation can be increased to get civil servants into professional government agencies (Solikin, 2019). The human resource development in question is the withdrawal, training, and promotion of positions or ranks. The performance of an institution such as the police, and the role of the leader, is one of the keys to the successful delivery of public services. Therefore, to realize the services of the police institution to the community, the performance of each member is needed professionally. This means that leaders in police institutions must be able to encourage their members to work at high levels of performance (Simamora, 2004).

Buentello et al. (2008), in "Exploring the Casual Relationship between Organizational Citizenship Behavior, Total Quality Management, and Performance," found that there is no direct relationship between Organizational Citizenship Behavior and Organizational Performance; in this case, Organizational Citizenship Behavior is not directly reflected in company performance. Yan & Yan (2013), in Leadership, Organizational Citizenship Behavior, and Innovation in Small Business: An Empirical Study, state that the different dimensions used in Organizational Citizenship Behavior will have different effects on different aspects of organizational performance. Podsakoff & MacKenzie (2006) say it consists of helping other employees without coercion (altruism), the performance of role requirements that exceed minimum standards (conscientiousness), voluntary participation and support for organizational functions both professionally and socially (civic virtue), and abstinence from making issues that can interfere in the work environment (sportsmanship). According to Filstad & Karp (2020), leadership as a practice requires the importance of structural, cultural, and contextual conditions, as well as the emerging and dynamic nature of leadership practices. Serfontein and Hough (2011), in the Relationship Between Strategic Leadership, Operational Strategy, and Organizational Performance, argue that strategic leadership has a significant effect on operational excellence and performance in business organizations in South Africa.

The method related to latent variables is structural equation modeling (SEM) (Brown, 2006; Awalk, 2009; Raykov & Marcoulides, 2006; Hair et al., 2010; Bollen, 1989). Black (2015), researched the quality of effective leadership in higher education. Gusmao et al. (2018) researched the effect of OCB on performance. N. Rusdi et al. (2018), SEM on business performance. This study examines the organizational performance of the PNTL in the Government of Timor-Leste by examining the influence of organizational performance resulting from strategic leadership, organizational learning, and organizational culture, with organizational citizenship behavior as an intervening variable using structural equation modeling (SEM). This research is expected to increase optimal performance by the principles of completing work by time, quantity, quality, planning, and cooperation determined by the institution or department. More efforts are needed, including strategic leadership that can

become the driving force that drives change in organizations, efforts to increase the ability of employees through organizational learning, and maintaining a conducive organizational culture, which in turn can improve the performance of PNTL

2. Method

The data in this study used primary data, namely, a survey at the Timor-Leste PNTL Office. Exogenous latent variables consist of strategic leadership, organizational learning, organizational culture, intervening latent variables, namely organizational citizenship behavior, and endogenous latent variables, namely organizational performance. The questionnaires distributed contained several statement items related to the research variables. There are 5 alternative answers given according to the Likert scale, namely: 1 = Strongly Disagree; 2 = Disagree; 3 = Disagree; 4 = Agree; 5 = Strongly Agree. The research conceptual framework is presented in Figure 1.

Structural equation modeling is used to thoroughly explain the relationship between variables in the study (Hair Jr. et al., 2010). There are six steps in conducting SEM analysis, starting with establishing individual constructs, determining measurement models, assessing the reliability and validity of measurement models, determining structural models, assessing the validity of structural models, and making conclusions and recommendations (Otok et al., 2021). The stages of the analysis carried out are the evaluation of the measurement model, the goodness of fit, and the evaluation of the structural model. Evaluation of the measurement model, namely convergent validity, is used to determine the correlation between each indicator and its latent variables (Hidayat, 2022). Convergent validity is declared valid if the value of the standardized loading factor is greater than 0.5, while discriminant validity is seen from the root value of the average variance extracted (AVE), which is greater than 0.5 (Lefrandt et al., 2022). Composite reliability (C-R) is an indicator block that measures a construct and can be evaluated by measuring internal consistency. Composite reliability can be accepted for its level of reliability if the coefficient of the latent variable is greater than 0.7. After testing the validity and reliability of each latent variable, several prerequisites that must be met in structural modeling are the normal multivariate assumption, the assumption that there is no multicollinearity or singularity, and the assumption that there are no outliers (Hair Jr. et al., 2010). The next stage is making conclusions based on the results of hypothesis testing on structural coefficients and model fit.

Figure 1: The impact of the strategic leadership conceptual model, organizational learning, and organizational culture on organizational performance with organizational citizenship Intervening variables in behavior

3. Results

The measurement model includes convergent validity test, discriminant validity and reliability test. In detail, the validity and reliability of each indicator and latent variable are presented in Table 1.

Table 1 shows that the latent variables Strategic Leadership (X1), Organizational Learning (X2), Organizational Culture (X3), Organizational Citizenship Behavior (Y1), and Organizational Performance (Y2) provide loading factors, AVE roots, and Composite Reliability (C-R) values above the cut-off value so that they can be said to be validly convergent, validly discriminant, and reliable. Likewise, for each indicator, all p-value variance errors are smaller than 0.05, so it can be said that all indicators and latent variables are reliable. Strategic Leadership (X1) is formed by the indicators of the ability to manage change (X1.2) (0.933), the ability to build cooperation and a sense of belonging (X1.3) (0.887), visionary thinking (X1.1) (0.786), and the ability to think strategically (X1.4) (0.635). Organizational learning (X2) is formed by the indicators system thinking (X2.1) (0.912), mental modeling (X2.2) (0.912), learning team (X2.4) (0.910), personal mastery (X2.3) (0.898) and shared vision (X2.5) (0.854). Organizational Performance (Y2) is formed by the indicators of Service Quality (Y2.2) (0.922), Responsibility (Y2.4) (0.921), Accountability (Y2.5) (0.921), Productivity (Y2.1) (0.913), and Responsiveness (Y2.3) (0.864).

Likewise, for each indicator, all p-value variance errors are smaller than 0.05, so it can be said that all indicators and latent variables are reliable. Strategic Leadership (X1) is formed by the indicators of the ability to manage change (X1.2) (0.933), the ability to build cooperation and a sense of belonging (X1.3) (0.887), visionary thinking (X1.1) (0.786), and the ability to think strategically (X1.4) (0.635). Organizational learning (X2) is formed by the indicators system thinking (X2.1) (0.912), mental modeling (X2.2) (0.912), learning team (X2.4) (0.910), personal mastery (X2.3) (0.898), and shared vision (X2.5) (0.854). Organizational culture (X3) is formed by indicators of bureaucratic culture (X3.3) (0.950), innovative culture (X3.1) (0.922), and supportive culture (X3.2) (0.915). Organizational Citizenship Behavior (Y1) is formed by the indicators Willingness to Tolerate without Complaint (Y1.3) (0.977), Involvement in Organizational Functions (Y1.4) (0.977), Behavior Helping Colleagues (Y1.1) (0.853), and Behavior Complying with Work Rules and Procedures (Y1.2) (0.839). Organizational Performance (Y2) is formed by the indicators of Service Quality (Y2.2) (0.922), Responsibility (Y2.4) (0.921), Accountability (Y2.5) (0.921), Productivity (Y2.1) (0.913), and Responsiveness (Y2.3) (0.864).

Table 1: Testing the validity and reliability of research variables

Latent Variable	Indicator	P variance error	Loading (λ)	λ^2	1 - λ^2	C-R (AVE) [Root AVE]
<i>Strategic Leadership</i> (X1)	Visionary (X1.1)	0.000	0.786	0.618	0.382	0.888 (0.670) [0.818]
	Ability to manage change (X1.2)	0.000	0.933	0.870	0.130	
	Ability to build cooperation and a sense of belonging (X1.3)	0.000	0.887	0.787	0.213	
	Ability to think strategically (X1.4)	0.000	0.635	0.403	0.597	
<i>Organizational Learning</i> (X2)	Systems thinking (X2.1)	0.000	0.912	0.832	0.168	0.954 (0.805) [0.897]
	Mental Models (X2.2)	0.000	0.912	0.832	0.168	
	Personal mastery (X2.3)	0.000	0.898	0.806	0.194	
	Learning Team (X2.4)	0.000	0.910	0.828	0.172	
	Shared vision (X2.5)	0.000	0.854	0.729	0.271	
<i>Organizational Culture</i> (X3)	Innovative Culture (X3.1)	0.000	0.922	0.850	0.150	0.950 (0.863) [0.929]
	Supportive Culture (X3.2)	0.000	0.915	0.837	0.163	
	Bureaucratic culture (X3.3)	0.000	0.950	0.902	0.098	
<i>Organizational Citizenship Behavior</i> (Y1)	Behavior Helping Colleagues (Y1.1)	0.000	0.853	0.728	0.272	0.953 (0.835) [0.914]
	Behavior Complying with Work Rules and Procedures (Y1.2)	0.000	0.839	0.704	0.296	
<i>Organizational Performance</i> (Y2)	Willingness to Tolerate without Complaint (Y1.3)	0.001	0.977	0.955	0.045	

	Involvement in Organizational Functions (Y1.4)	0.002	0.977	0.955	0.045
	Productivity (Y2.1)	0.000	0.913	0.834	0.166
Organizational Performance (Y2)	Quality of service (Y2.2)	0.000	0.922	0.850	0.150 0.959
	Responsiveness (Y2.3)	0.000	0.864	0.746	0.254 (0.825)
	Responsibility (Y2.4)	0.000	0.921	0.848	0.152 [0.908]
	Accountability (Y2.5)	0.000	0.921	0.848	0.152

After testing the validity and reliability of each latent variable, several prerequisites that must be met in structural modeling are the normal multivariate assumption, the assumption that there are no multicollinearity or singularity, and outliers. The results of the data normality test on all research variables give a multivariate critical ratio value of 1.710, and this value lies beyond -1.96 and 1.96, so it can be said that the data is normally distributed multivariate. Singularity can be seen in the determinant of the covariance matrix. The results of the study provide a determinant value of the sample covariance matrix of 0.107. This value is not close to zero, so it can be said that there is no singularity problem in the data being analyzed. Multicollinearity can be seen through the correlation between exogenous latent variables. The results of the study provide a p-value for each exogenous latent variable, namely: (X1 with X2 of 0.703), (X2 with X3 of 0.737), and (X1 with X3 of 0.704). This value is greater than a = 0.05, so it can be said that there is no multicollinearity problem in the data being analyzed. Outliers are observations that appear with extreme values in a univariate or multivariate manner. Outlier test results in this study are presented at Mahalanobis distance or Mahalanobis d-squared. The Mahalanobis value that is greater than the Chi-square table, or the p1 value of 0.001, is said to be an outlier observation. There were three outliers in this study, but because they accounted for less than 5% of the observations, it could be said that there were no outliers.

Furthermore, the form of the Organizational Performance model path diagram is presented as follows:

Figure 2: Strategic Leadership, Organizational Learning, and Organizational Culture Relationship Model to Organizational Performance with Organizational Citizenship Intervening variables in behavior

The complete results of testing the measurement model with the AMOS program can be seen in the following table:

Table 2: Results of Strategic Leadership, Organizational Learning, and Organizational Culture Testing Models on Organizational Performance with Organizational Citizenship Behavior of intervening variables

Goodness of Fit (GoF)	Cut-Off value	The calculation results	Information
Chi – Square	Expected to be small	201.168	χ^2 with df = 176 is 207.955 Good
Significance Probability	$\geq 0,05$	0.094	Good
RMSEA	$\leq 0,08$	0.069	Good
GFI	$\geq 0,90$	0.938	Good
AGFI	$\geq 0,90$	0.858	Marginal
CMIN/DF	$\leq 2,00$	1.143	Good
TLI	$\geq 0,90$	0.962	Good
CFI	$\geq 0,90$	0.968	Good

From the appropriate model, it can be interpreted for each path coefficient through the following structural equation:

$$Y_1 = 0.231X_1 + 0.463X_2 + 0.250X_3 \quad (1)$$

$$Y_2 = 0.239X_1 + 0.259X_2 + 0.200X_3 + 0.236Y_1 \quad (2)$$

with,

X_1 : Strategic Leadership

X_2 : Organizational Learning

X_3 : Organizational Culture

Y_1 : Organizational Citizenship Behavior

Y_2 : Organizational Performance

The path coefficient test in Figure 2 and the above equations are presented in detail in the following table:

Table 3: Results of Pathway Coefficient Testing of Strategic Leadership, Organizational Learning, and Organizational Culture Models on Organizational Performance with Organizational Citizenship Behavior intervening variables

Variables	Coefficient	C.R.	Prob.	Information
Strategic Leadership (X1)→ Organizational Citizenship Behavior (Y1)	0.231	2.259	0.024	Significant
Organizational Learning (X2)→ Organizational Citizenship Behavior (Y1)	0.463	4.311	0.000	Significant
Organizational Culture (X3)→ Organizational Citizenship Behavior (Y1)	0.250	2.700	0.007	Significant
Strategic Leadership (X1)→ Organizational Performance (Y2)	0.239	2.257	0.024	Significant
Organizational Learning (X2)→ Organizational Performance (Y2)	0.259	2.168	0.030	Significant
Organizational Culture (X3)→ Organizational Performance (Y2)	0.200	2.076	0.038	Significant
Organizational Citizenship Behavior (Y1) → Organizational Performance (Y2)	0.236	2.072	0.038	Significant

Based on Table 3, the interpretation of each path coefficient is as follows:

a. *The Influence of Strategic Leadership (X1) on Organizational Citizenship Behavior (Y1)*

Strategic leadership (X1) has a positive and significant effect on organizational citizenship behavior (Y1). This can be seen from the path coefficient, which has a positive sign of 0.231 with a C.R. equal to 2.259 and obtained

a significance probability (p) of 0.024, which is smaller than the significance level (α), which is determined at 0.05. Thus, strategic leadership (X_1) has a direct effect on organizational citizenship behavior (Y_1) of 0.231, which means that every time there is an increase in strategic leadership (X_1), it will increase organizational citizenship behavior (Y_1). This is by Sugiharjo (2020), Obiwuru et al. (2011), Khan et al. (2013), and Bagyo (2013), which state that effective leadership contributions to employee commitment and high employee citizenship behavior are influential factors in the success of OCB.

b. The Influence of Organizational Learning (X_2) on Organizational Citizenship Behavior (Y_1)

Organizational learning (X_2) has a positive and significant effect on organizational citizenship behavior (Y_1). This can be seen from the path coefficient, which has a positive sign of 0.463 with a C.R. equal to 4,311 and obtained a significance probability (p) of 0.000, which is smaller than the significance level (α), which was determined at 0.05. Thus, organizational learning (X_2) has a direct effect on organizational citizenship behavior (Y_1) of 0.463, which means that every time there is an increase in organizational learning (X_2), it will increase organizational citizenship behavior (Y_1). This is to the research of Somech and Drach-Zahavy (2004), which states that organizational learning has a positive relationship with OCB that benefits the organization as a whole, and certain individuals.

c. The Influence of Organizational Culture (X_3) on Organizational Citizenship Behavior (Y_1)

Organizational culture (X_3) has a positive and significant effect on organizational citizenship behavior (Y_1). This can be seen from the path coefficient, which has a positive sign of 0.250 with a C.R. of 2,700 and a significance probability (p) of 0.007, which is smaller than the significance level (α), which is determined at 0.05. Thus, organizational culture (X_3) has a direct effect on organizational citizenship behavior (Y_1) of 0.250, which means that every time there is an increase in organizational culture (X_3), it will increase organizational citizenship behavior (Y_1). This is in line with research conducted by Gusmau et al. (2018) and Guo et al. (2021), which state that organizational culture has a positive influence on organizational citizenship behavior and its indicators.

d. The Influence of Strategic Leadership (X_1) on Organizational Performance (Y_2)

Strategic leadership (X_1) has a positive and significant effect on organizational performance (Y_2). This can be seen from the path coefficient, which is positive at 0.239 with a C.R. equal to 2,259, and the obtained significance probability (p) of 0.024, which is smaller than the significance level (α), which was determined at 0.05. Thus, strategic leadership (X_1) has a direct effect on organizational performance (Y_2) of 0.239, which means that every time there is an increase in strategic leadership (X_1), it will increase organizational performance (Y_2). This is in line with research conducted by Serfontein & Hought (2011) and Pazireh et al. (2014), which state that strategic leadership can have an effect on organizational performance through understanding work and environmental conditions and can build interaction with employees.

e. The Influence of Organizational Learning (X_2) on Organizational Performance (Y_2)

Organizational learning (X_2) has a positive and significant effect on organizational performance (Y_2). This can be seen from the path coefficient, which is positive at 0.259 with a C.R. of 2.168 and obtained a significance probability (p) of 0.030, which is smaller than the significance level (α), which was determined at 0.05. Thus, organizational learning (X_2) has a direct effect on organizational performance (Y_2) of 0.259, which means that every time there is an increase in organizational learning (X_2), it will increase organizational performance (Y_2). This is in line with the results of research by Real et al. (2006), which states that organizational learning influences organizational performance.

f. The Influence of Organizational Culture (X_3) on Organizational Performance (Y_2)

Organizational culture (X_3) has a positive and significant effect on organizational performance (Y_2). This can be seen from the path coefficient, which has a positive sign of 0.200 with a C.R. of 2.076 and a significance probability (p) of 0.038, which is smaller than the significance level (α), which is determined at 0.05. Thus, organizational culture (X_3) has a direct effect on organizational performance (Y_2) of 0.200, which means that

every time there is an increase in organizational culture (X3), it will increase organizational performance (Y2). This is in line with the results of Darsana's research (2013), which states that organizational work culture influences performance.

g. The Influence of Organizational Citizenship Behavior (Y1) on Organizational Performance (Y2)

Organizational citizenship behavior (Y1) has a positive and significant effect on organizational performance (Y2). This can be seen from the path coefficient, which has a positive sign of 0.236 with a C.R. equal to 2.072 and obtained a significance probability (p) of 0.038, which is smaller than the significance level (α), which was determined at 0.05. Thus, organizational citizenship behavior (Y1) has a direct effect on organizational performance (Y2) of 0.236, which means that every time there is an increase in organizational citizenship behavior (Y1), it will increase organizational performance (Y2). The results of this study are in line with research conducted by Kolade et al. (2014), Wang (2014), and Fitriastuti (2013), which states that organizational members are the most important resource in the organization.

4. Conclusion

Based on data analysis, results, and discussion, this research can be concluded as follows:

- a. The organizational performance model with organizational citizenship behavior as an intervening variable based on the Timor Leste PNTL is a fit model based on the goodness of fit (GoF) criteria.
- b. The dominant indicators of strategic leadership are the ability to manage change, the ability to build cooperation and a sense of belonging, and the ability to be visionary.
- c. The dominant indicators in organizational learning are systems thinking, mental models, learning teams, and personal mastery.
- d. The dominant indicators of organizational culture are bureaucratic culture, innovative culture, and supportive culture.
- e. Dominant indicators of organizational citizenship behavior are willing to tolerate without complaining and involvement in organizational functions.
- f. The dominant indicators of organizational performance are service quality, responsibility, accountability, and productivity.
- g. Organizational performance is influenced by organizational citizenship behavior, strategic leadership, organizational learning, and organizational culture. Furthermore, organizational citizenship behavior is influenced by strategic leadership, organizational learning, and organizational culture.

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